

**PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE
DEVELOPMENT OF AUDITORY ABILITIES OF STUDENTS**

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Annotation. The article focuses on the development of new methods and techniques in the formation of students' auditory competence in English using multimedia tools, analysis of existing methods in two languages and new research to further develop students' auditory skills.

Key words. Multimedia, auditory speech, the silent way, total- physical response

Introduction.

It is necessary to summarize the spiritual, ideological, pedagogical research conducted in Uzbekistan during the years of independence, to bring them to a holistic concept, to form the scientific and practical content of pedagogical innovation, to determine its components and directions. In this regard, modern staff must know one or more foreign languages within their specialization. From this point of view, it is important to increase the auditing ability of students studying in general secondary schools of the country in the process of learning English. Because listening is an integral part of speaking. Our observations show that while a certain amount of time is allocated in schools for teaching foreign languages, speaking, reading, and writing, very little time is spent on a methodological approach to listening. However, listening as the main form of speech activity plays an important role in the process of real communication. Listening is an independent, necessary and challenging speaking activity for students.

"In modern society, 45% of people listen, 30% speak, 16% read, 9% write," says Russian scientist Galskova N.D. There is a minimum amount of time for listening in English classes. Therefore, in speech activity, students' auditory speech is defined as a symbiosis of communicative and action orientation. Audit activity consists of a set of scientific, technological, organizational, financial, commercial measures aimed at the creation of a new product, the purpose of which is to transfer the accumulated knowledge, skills, abilities, technology and tools to the large-scale production of this new product. and ensure its effectiveness. Our observations in the study showed that the development of students' auditory skills in English lessons, which are important for their future activities, is often associated with their listening and listening processes. However, today in pedagogical practice it has been revealed that there are a number of controversial issues in the development of students' professional audit ability. They are:

-While learning English, students try to translate them into another language because they are familiar with the mechanisms of learning the native language. As a result, there are difficulties in communicative and linguistic description of language acquisition. There are also semantic difficulties in assimilating information;

- Morphological means of speech in the integration of syntactic and pragmatic factors for the acquisition of speech in another language

- the need for long-term exercise, as there are difficulties in the perception of the lexical and syntactic forms on the basis of formative, re-understanding in the brain and understanding its meaning;

- Lack of systematization of various didactic tasks and exercises in auditory teaching;

- Lexical and grammatical tasks on language acquisition in textbooks and manuals are not aimed at the development of certain competencies;

- the meaning of grammatical forms in the process of interaction of linguistic and pragmatic factors in the reception of information in another language is not

clearly systematized by the relevant lexical units (communication, speech, written and oral);

- The student is not forced to be indifferent during the lesson, to think independently, to create and research, etc.

An analysis of the literature shows that in order for students to master speech in another language, it is possible, first of all, to develop their speaking skills and, on this basis, to develop their spoken language communication. When studying scientific sources, literature analysis, and English language practice, students should be given a certain amount of assignments during the session for auditory speech, oral presentation, reading, and writing.

In developing students' auditory competence, speech activities take place in four main stages: planning, organizing, guiding, and supervising. If this consistency is fully implemented by teachers, existing barriers to the development of auditory competence can be successfully addressed.

The process of deciding what methods to use (functional) to assign (distribute) tasks to master the auditory speech in English is called work organization. The development of audit capacity is effective due to the correct implementation of the planning and organizational steps. It is known from practice that the real work of teachers does not always correspond to the students assigned to them. For joint work to be effective:

- First, the executors must have a good understanding of when and what results are expected from them;

- Second, they are interested in achieving the expected result;

- Third, they are satisfied with their work;

-Fourth, the socio-psychological environment in the team must be conducive to effective work.

Thus, the interest of teachers in effective work, to ensure their satisfaction, to maintain a favorable socio-psychological environment in the community is called leadership. In the development of speech activities, even if the joint activities are

well planned and organized, the manager should be able to respond in a timely manner to changes, and to have sufficient information. It is necessary to take a special management action called control to obtain such information and determine the need to make adjustments to the course of the case. Planning, organizing, teaching and monitoring is a complex structure that includes situation analysis, forecasting, goal setting, performance appraisal, and decision-making on the selection of any work plan. . In order to develop students' auditory ability, it is necessary to organize activities in a new and convenient way, with less effort and time, to achieve more results, without spending too much mental and physical effort.

The study also explored the use of different methods in developing students' auditory competence. In doing so, they:

-The traditional method

-Interactive methods

- Use of language cabinets

-Developed methods based on information and communication Computerized methods

-Programmed methods

- The author's methods of advanced pedagogues were developed by teachers of foreign languages working in higher education institutions and used personal authorship methods. The results of the analysis show that 67% of teachers still use traditional methods in their work.

The use of all types of multimedia electronic programs in the organization of English language lessons is the basis for increasing the efficiency of the learning process and creating great opportunities for students to learn independently. In the development of their auditory ability (colloquial speech) and written ("reading") it is important to use methods that facilitate the knowledge and perception of the sound layer and lexical layer of speech. We analyzed such techniques as part of the study.

The Silent Way originated in the 1960s. This method involves the use of natural factors in learning English. Everyone has the ability to learn a language

naturally. Accordingly, if a student wants to learn English perfectly, it is necessary to create all the pedagogical conditions for him. Therefore, in the opinion of the proponents of this method, the English teacher should create conditions for the realization of the student's potential. The teacher increases the student's language skills by showing, reading and listening to different symbols of words. Characters are then stored in memory in conjunction with words¹.

"Total-physical response" (a method of physically affecting information). As a result of this method, any information that has not been processed will not be stored in memory. Therefore, in order to learn a foreign language, a person must pass the language information. Accordingly, first the student is equipped with a sufficient amount of information in a foreign language. Then, for about twenty hours, the student regularly listens to a foreign language material consisting only of a given set of information. The student is then required to respond physically to the information received. The response goes through body movements. For example, “Stand up!” When students say, “Sit down!” students sit down. Therefore, an active relationship with this information is established only after the student has heard for a long time and then assimilated the information through his actions. In this method, students then interact not only with the teacher, but also actively.

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